

Individual Handwritten Basic Bengali Character Recognition Using Supervised Machine Learning SVM Algorithm

Submitted by

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Session: 2015-16

A project report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

Electrical and Electronic Engineering

University of Dhaka

Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh

April, 2017

Certificate of Approval

*I am certifying that, the project work entitled “**Individual handwritten basic Bengali character recognition using supervised Machine Learning SVM algorithm**” submitted by Tarek Bin Zahid, for the partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science (Hons.) in Electrical and Electronic Engineering offered by University of Dhaka during the academic year 2015-2016 is an original work carried by the student under my supervision, meets acceptable presentation standard and this work has not formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma or such other titles.*

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Declaration

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “**Individual handwritten basic Bengali character recognition using supervised Machine Learning SVM algorithm**” is a record of original work done by me, except where otherwise acknowledged, and this is submitted in the partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science (Hons.) in Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Dhaka. The results embodied in this project report in whole or in part have not been submitted for an award, including a higher degree to any other University or Institution.

Name: Tarek Bin Zahid

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Tarek Bin Zahid', written in a cursive style. The signature starts with a long horizontal stroke that curves down and loops back, followed by several smaller loops and a final horizontal stroke.

Date: 02/ 04/ 2017

Acknowledgements

On the very outset of this project report, I would like to show gratitude to our Almighty creator for our complete project work. Then I would like to extend my sincere and heartfelt obligation towards all the personages who have helped me in this endeavour. Without their active guidance, help, cooperation and encouragement, I would not have made headway in the project.

I am ineffably indebted to Lecturer Miftahul Jannat Rasna for conscientious guidance and encouragement to accomplish this assignment.

I am extremely thankful and pay my gratitude to my department for giving me this opportunity.

I also acknowledge with a deep sense of reverence, my gratitude towards my parents and members of my family, who has always supported me morally as well as economically.

At last but not least gratitude goes to all of my friends, seniors who directly or indirectly helped me to complete this project report.

Abstract

Handwritten character recognition is a classic machine learning problem. But very few scientific work regarding character recognition involving Bengali characters have been done in the past years. The aim of this paper was to train a model that can detect individual basic Bengali characters. Our result shows SVM gives higher accuracy than any other classifiers. We did our project ground up, collecting data from the students of our department, combining those with other externally sourced dataset. Preprocessing is performed on the dataset to remove the data of any noise and prepare it to be feed into the model. By a pixel based approach we trained the model as opposed to a feature based model. Our results suggest that using a SVM classifier best suits our job with an accuracy of 86.7%. We also explored further applications of the model by connecting it with an input device such as webcam.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.2	MACHINE LEARNING VS. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.....	1
1.3	HOW MACHINE LEARNING WORKS.....	2
1.4	A BRIEF HISTORY OF MACHINE LEARNING MILESTONES	2
1.5	AIMS AND OBJECTIVES	4
1.6	LITERATURE SURVEY.....	4
1.7	1.7 PROJECT OUTLINE.....	5
2	Different Techniques of Machine Learning	6
2.1	INTRODUCTION	6
2.2	WHEN TO CONSIDER USING ML.....	7
2.3	DECIDING WHICH ALGORITHM TO USE.....	7
2.4	COMMON MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS.....	7
2.5	SUMMARY.....	12
3	Support Vector Machine	13
3.1	INTRODUCTION.....	13
3.2	DECISION BOUNDARY.....	14
3.3	KEY POINTS TO REMEMBER	16
3.4	KERNEL METHODS.....	16
3.5	SVM NON LINEAR CLASSIFIER.....	16
3.6	ADVANTAGES & DISADVANTAGES	17
3.6.1	ADVANTAGE OF SVM CLASSIFIER.....	17
3.6.2	DISADVANTAGE OF SVM CLASSIFIER	17
3.7	SVM APPLICATIONS.....	17
4	Matlab Implementation	19
4.1	INTRODUCTION	19
4.2	APPROACH.....	19
4.3	CHOOSING THE RIGHT APPLICATION FOR THE JOB.....	20
4.4	DATA COLLECTION	20
4.5	DATA PREPROCESSING.....	26
4.5.1	DATA CLEANING	27
4.5.2	DATA INTEGRATION.....	28

4.5.3	DATA TRANSFORMATION.....	31
4.5.4	DATA REDUCTION/ DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION.....	34
4.6	DEFINING CLASS.....	35
4.7	TRAINING THE MODEL.....	37
4.7.1	ADVANCED TECHNIQUES PERFORMED ON CUBIC SVM.....	38
4.7.2	PARTICULARS ABOUT THE CHOSEN CLASSIFIER.....	39
4.8	SUMMARY	39
5	Performance Results Analysis	41
5.1	INTRODUCTION.....	41
5.2	CONFUSION MATRIX.....	41
5.3	ROC CURVE	44
5.4	MANUAL DATA INPUT.....	47
5.5	SUMMARY	47
6	Conclusion	49
6.1	INTRODUCTION.....	49
6.2	SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE.....	49
6.3	MATLAB IMPLEMENTATION.....	49
6.4	PERFORMANCE RESULTS ANALYSIS.....	50
6.5	LIMITATIONS	51
6.6	IMPROVEMENT OF CURRENT MODEL.....	52
6.7	PRACTICAL USE.....	52
	Appendix A.....	53
	Appendix B.....	53
	Appendix C.....	53
	BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	56

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Machine learning teaches computers to do what comes naturally to humans and animals: learn from experience. Machine learning algorithms use computational methods to “learn” information directly from data without relying on a predetermined equation as a model or being explicitly coded to solve a problem. The algorithms adaptively improve their performance as the number of samples available for learning increases. Applications of machine learning, but not limited to, range from autonomous driving, facial recognition, music generation, fraud detection, speech recognition, publish reports and even finding terrorist suspects.

Over the years, machine learning algorithms have quite subtly implemented themselves into modern products like recommendation engines (Google, Bing, Amazon, and Netflix), speech recognition (Google Now, Apple Siri) and personal assistant (Amazon Alexa, Google Siri, and Microsoft Cortana).

1.2 MACHINE LEARNING VS. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

People tend to use machine learning and artificial intelligence as if they’re interchangeable, but they’re not: rather, machine learning (ML) is one very successful approach to the broader field of artificial intelligence (AI). [1]

Artificial intelligence is, essentially, the simulation of intelligence in computers. It encompasses a range of approaches, which range from the simple to the incredibly complex.

Machine learning, on the other hand, is a form of artificial intelligence in which the computer learns for itself how to complete a task.

1.3 HOW MACHINE LEARNING WORKS

Machine learning system consists of three major parts: Model, Parameters, and Learner.

Model: the system that makes predictions or identifications.

Parameters: the signals or factors used by the model to form its decisions.

Learner: the system that adjusts the parameters — and in turn the model — by looking at differences in predictions versus actual outcome.

Suppose we want to build a model that will identify cats from pictures. The problem as easy as it sounds for a human is immensely difficult for computer to understand. There is no clear formula or equation to represent cats to computer. So we design a model of likely factors or parameters that a cat might have, namely weight, size and so on. Then we feed the model large amounts of pictures of cats. The learner makes adjustment so to decrease the difference (or cost!) between the predicted result and actual result. The iteration with several algorithms until the model can predict within a reasonable margin of accuracy.

1.4 A BRIEF HISTORY OF MACHINE LEARNING MILESTONES [2]

1950 — Alan Turing creates the “Turing Test” to determine if a computer has real intelligence. To pass the test, a computer must be able to fool a human into believing it is also human.

1952 — Arthur Samuel wrote the first computer learning program. The program was the game of checkers, and the IBM computer improved at the game the more it played, studying which moves made up winning strategies and incorporating those moves into its program.

1957 — Frank Rosenblatt designed the first neural network for computers (the perceptron), which simulate the thought processes of the human brain.

1967 — The “nearest neighbor” algorithm was written, allowing computers to begin using very basic pattern recognition. This could be used to map a route for traveling salesmen, starting at a random city but ensuring they visit all cities during a short tour.

1979 — Students at Stanford University invent the “Stanford Cart” which can navigate obstacles in a room on its own.

1981 — Gerald Dejong introduces the concept of Explanation Based Learning (EBL), in which a computer analyses training data and creates a general rule it can follow by discarding unimportant data.

1985 — Terry Sejnowski invents NetTalk, which learns to pronounce words the same way a baby does.

1990s — Work on machine learning shifts from a knowledge-driven approach to a data-driven approach. Scientists begin creating programs for computers to analyze large amounts of data and draw conclusions — or “learn” — from the results.

1997 — IBM’s Deep Blue beats the world champion at chess.

2006 — Geoffrey Hinton coins the term “deep learning” to explain new algorithms that let computers “see” and distinguish objects and text in images and videos.

2010 — The Microsoft Kinect can track 20 human features at a rate of 30 times per second, allowing people to interact with the computer via movements and gestures.

2011 — IBM’s Watson beats its human competitors at Jeopardy.

2011 — Google Brain is developed, and its deep neural network can learn to discover and categorize objects much the way a cat does.

2012 – Google’s X Lab develops a machine learning algorithm that is able to autonomously browse YouTube videos to identify the videos that contain cats.

2014 – Facebook develops DeepFace, a software algorithm that is able to recognize or verify individuals on photos to the same level as humans can.

2015 – Amazon launches its own machine learning platform.

2015 – Microsoft creates the Distributed Machine Learning Toolkit, which enables the efficient distribution of machine learning problems across multiple computers.

2015 – Over 3,000 AI and Robotics researchers, endorsed by Stephen Hawking, Elon Musk and Steve Wozniak (among many others), sign an open letter warning of the danger of autonomous weapons which select and engage targets without human intervention.

2016 – Google’s artificial intelligence algorithm beats a professional player at the Chinese board game Go, which is considered the world’s most complex board game and is many times harder than chess. The AlphaGo algorithm developed by Google DeepMind managed to win five games out of five in the Go competition.

1.5 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Character recognition is a classic supervised classification machine learning problem. Many academic and research works have been done and published on English characters but unfortunately very few on Bengali characters. We take on this opportunity to train a model that can recognize handwritten individual basic characters (vowels) of Bengali language.

Handwritten characters are harder to recognize since they vary by person, style, and do not have any specific pattern.

The aim of this project is to:

- Use machine learning to train a model which can detect individual handwritten characters with reasonable accuracy.
- Employ different techniques and algorithms and finally select the best model.
- Analyze the accuracy of the model.
- Connect the model with any input device and explore practical application.

1.6 LITERATURE SURVEY

In the recent years, machine learning has been highly popularized by Professor Andrew Ng of Stanford University. He is recognized as a pioneer in artificial intelligence. His course ‘Machine Learning’ on Coursera has inspired thousands of engineers to start their career in machine learning. My first exposure to machine learning was through this course and which ultimately earned me an online degree on machine learning by Stanford University. This course is highly technical and focuses highly on hands-on application of the concept. As a requirement of the course I had to build a model to train handwritten numeric English characters using a neural network. The task was completed with Matlab without help from classification learner app, manually calculating the gradient descent and cost function of each iteration.

‘Machine Learning - The Art and Science of Algorithms that Make Sense of Data’ by Peter Flach provides an excellent grounding for anyone new to machine learning. This book covers the theoretical aspects, for someone who wants to dig deeper and possibly build new algorithms.

‘Data Mining – Practical Machine Learning Tools and Technique’ by Ian H. Witten, Eibe Frank and Mark A. Hall approaches machine learning through a more practical approach. This book contains several ways to collect and process the data.

‘Digital Image Processing Using MATLAB’ by Rafael C. Gonzalez is a very popular book which uses Matlab as an application of choice for image processing. Contents from this book were found to be of immense help in understanding certain parts of data preprocessing like noise removal.

‘A Comparison of Feature and Pixel-based Methods for Recognizing Handwritten Bangla Digits’ - Olarik Surinta, Lambert Schomaker and Marco Wiering, Institute of Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Engineering, University of Groningen, The Netherlands – a paper which explored a pixel based method on numeric Bengali numeric characters and compared with features based method. While most cases of character recognition are feature based, this paper took an approach to compare between the two methods.

1.7 PROJECT OUTLINE

The project paper is outlined below:

- Chapter 1 provides brief introduction of machine learning, its application history and introduces the problem this project is about.
- Chapter 2 provides deeper information about popular machine learning algorithms that are currently in use and their specific applications in the industry.
- Chapter 3 provides detailed discussion on our preferred learning algorithm that we have used on our project and also serves as a basis for the theoretical aspect of our project.
- Chapter 4 provides detailed description about the practical aspect of the project. It includes the software we have used, the techniques, data collection, processing and the results.
- Chapter 5 provides further discussion on the results and the performance of the model.
- Chapter 6 concludes our project with general discussion on the whole project, our success on solving the problem and motivation for future work.

Chapter 2

Different Techniques of Machine Learning

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Machine learning draws conclusions by learning from data. Recent advancement in processing power and storage facility leads to emerging progress towards machine learning. There are mainly two types of learning methods: supervised, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning and reinforcement learning.

A supervised learning algorithm takes a known set of input data (the training set) and known responses to the data (output), and trains a model to generate reasonable predictions for the response to new input data. Supervised learning is used if there is existing data for the output we are trying to predict. Supervised learning uses classification and regression techniques to develop predictive models.

Classification techniques predict discrete responses, for example, whether an email is genuine or spam, or whether a tumor is cancerous or benign. Classification models classify input data into categories. Typical applications include medical imaging, speech recognition, and credit scoring.

Regression techniques predict continuous responses, for example, changes in temperature or fluctuations in power demand. Typical applications include electricity load forecasting and algorithmic trading.

Unsupervised learning is useful when we want to explore data but don't yet have a specific goal or are not sure what information the data contains. It's also a good way to reduce the dimensions of your data.

Unsupervised learning finds hidden patterns or intrinsic structures in data. It is used to draw inferences from datasets consisting of input data without labeled responses.

Clustering is the most common unsupervised learning technique. It is used for exploratory data analysis to find hidden patterns or groupings in data. Applications for clustering include gene sequence analysis, market research, and object recognition.

Semi-supervised learning falls between supervised and unsupervised learning technique. Typically it uses few labelled data and lots of unlabeled data for training.

Reinforcement learning is the problem of getting an agent to act in the world so as to maximize its rewards. For example, consider teaching a dog a new trick: you cannot tell it what to do, but you can reward/punish it if it does the right/wrong thing. It has to figure out what it did that made it get the reward/punishment, which is known as the credit assignment problem. We can use a similar

method to train computers to do many tasks, such as playing backgammon or chess, scheduling jobs, and controlling robot limbs.

For the scope of this project we will mainly focus on supervised and unsupervised learning techniques.

2.2 WHEN TO CONSIDER USING ML

Machine learning is a good option to consider in the following situations:

- Handwritten rules and equations are too complex e.g. facial recognition
- The rules of task are constantly changing e.g. fraud detection
- The nature of the data is constantly changing and the program needs to adapt e.g. energy demand forecasting

2.3 DECIDING WHICH ALGORITHM TO USE

Selecting a machine learning algorithm is a process of trial and error – the selection is often a tradeoff between these factors:

- Speed of training
- Memory usage
- Accuracy of prediction
- Transparency or interpretability

2.4 COMMON MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

LOGISTIC REGRESSION

Fits a model that can predict the probability of a binary response belonging to one class or the other. Because of its simplicity, logistic regression is commonly used as a starting point for binary classification problems.

Best used:

- When data can be clearly separated by a single, linear boundary
- As a baseline for evaluating more complex classification

Figure 2.1: Logistic Regression – Yes and No problem

k NEAREST NEIGHBOR (kNN)

kNN categorizes objects based on the classes of their nearest neighbors in the dataset. kNN predictions assume that objects near each other are similar. Distance metrics, such as Euclidean, city block, cosine, and Chebychev, are used to find the nearest neighbor.

Best used:

- When a simple algorithm is needed to establish benchmark learning rules
- When memory usage of the trained model is a lesser concern
- When prediction speed of the trained model is a lesser concern

Figure 2.2: kNN classification

SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE (SVM)

Classifies data by finding the linear decision boundary (hyperplane) that separates all data points of one class from those of the other class. The best hyperplane for an SVM is the one with the largest margin between the two classes, when the data is linearly separable. If the data is not linearly separable, a loss function is used to penalize points on the wrong side of the hyperplane.

SVMs sometimes use a kernel transform to transform nonlinearly separable data into higher dimensions where a linear decision boundary can be found.

Best used:

- For data that has exactly two classes (you can also use it for multiclass classification with a technique called error-correcting output codes)
- For high-dimensional, nonlinearly separable data
- When a classifier is needed that's simple, easy to interpret, and accurate

Figure 2.3: SVM classifier – Hyperplane separating positive and negative values

NEURAL NETWORK

Inspired by the human brain, a neural network consists of highly connected networks of neurons that relate the inputs to the desired outputs. The network is trained by iteratively modifying the strengths of the connections so that given inputs map to the correct response.

Best used:

- For modeling highly nonlinear systems
- When data is available incrementally and you wish to constantly update the model
- When there could be unexpected changes in your input data
- When model interpretability is not a key concern

Figure 2.4: Neural Network with 1 hidden layer

NAÏVE BAYES

A naive Bayes classifier assumes that the presence of a particular feature in a class is unrelated to the presence of any other feature. It classifies new data based on the highest probability of its belonging to a particular class.

Best used:

- For a small dataset containing many parameters
- Easy to interpret
- When the model will encounter scenarios that weren't in the training data, as is the case with many financial and medical applications

Figure 2.5: Naïve Bayes classification

LINEAR REGRESSION

Linear regression is a statistical modeling technique used to describe a continuous response variable as a linear function of one or more predictor variables. Because linear regression models are simple to interpret and easy to train, they are often the first model to be fitted to a new dataset.

Best used:

- When you need an algorithm that is easy to interpret and fast to fit
- As a baseline for evaluating other, more complex, regression models

Figure 2.6: Linear regression – connecting data points with linear co relation

k-MEANS

Partitions data into k number of mutually exclusive clusters. How well a point fits into a cluster is determined by the distance from that point to the cluster's center.

Best used:

- When the number of clusters is known
- For fast clustering of large data sets

Figure 2.7: k-Means clustering

HIERARCHICAL CLUSTERING

Produces nested sets of clusters by analyzing similarities between pairs of points and grouping objects into a binary, hierarchical tree.

Best used:

- When you don't know in advance how many clusters are in your data
- You want visualization to guide your selection

Figure 2.8: Hierarchical clustering

2.5 SUMMARY

Machine learning also has intimate ties to optimization: many learning problems are formulated as minimization of some loss function on a training set of examples. Loss functions express the discrepancy between the predictions of the model being trained and the actual problem instances (for example, in classification, one wants to assign a label to instances, and models are trained to correctly predict the pre-assigned labels of a set examples). The difference between the two fields arises from the goal of generalization: while optimization algorithms can minimize the loss on a training set, machine learning is concerned with minimizing the loss on unseen samples.

Chapter 3

Support Vector Machine

3.1 INTRODUCTION

For two-class, separable training data sets, there are lots of possible linear separators. Intuitively, a decision boundary drawn in the middle of the void between data items of the two classes seems better than one which approaches very close to examples of one or both classes. While some learning methods such as the perceptron algorithm find just any linear separator, others, like Naive Bayes, search for the best linear separator according to some criterion. The SVM in particular defines the criterion to be looking for a decision surface that is maximally far away from any data point. This distance from the decision surface to the closest data point determines the margin of the classifier. This method of construction necessarily means that the decision function for an SVM is fully specified by a (usually small) subset of the data which defines the position of the separator. These points are referred to as the support vectors (in a vector space, a point can be thought of as a vector between the origin and that point). Figure 3.1 shows the margin and support vectors for a sample problem. Other data points play no part in determining the decision surface that is chosen. [3]

Figure 3.1: The support vectors are the 5 points right up against the margin of the classifier.

3.2 DECISION BOUNDARY

Let us formalize an SVM with algebra. A decision hyperplane can be defined by an intercept term b and a decision hyperplane normal vector \vec{w} which is perpendicular to the hyperplane. This vector is commonly referred to in the machine learning literature as the weight vector. To choose among all the hyperplanes that are perpendicular to the normal vector, we specify the intercept term b . Because the hyperplane is perpendicular to the normal vector, all points \vec{x} on the hyperplane satisfy $\vec{w}^T \vec{x} = -b$. Now suppose that we have a set of training data points $\mathbb{D} = \{(\vec{x}_i, y_i)\}$, where each member is a pair of a point \vec{x}_i and a class label y_i corresponding to it. For SVMs, the two data classes are always named +1 and -1 and the intercept term is always explicitly represented as b (rather than being folded into the weight vector \vec{w} by adding an extra always-on feature). The math works out much more cleanly if you do things this way, as we will see almost immediately in the definition of functional margin. The linear classifier is then:

$$f(\vec{x}) = \text{sign}(\vec{w}^T \vec{x} + b)$$

A value of -1 indicates one class, and a value of +1 the other class.

Figure 3.2: The geometric margin of a point r and a decision boundary ρ .

In Figure 3.2, we denote by r this distance. We know that the shortest distance between a point and a hyperplane is perpendicular to the plane, and hence, parallel to \vec{w} . A unit vector in this direction is $\vec{w}/|\vec{w}|$. The dotted line in the diagram is then a translation of the vector $r\vec{w}/|\vec{w}|$. Let us label the point on the hyperplane closest to \vec{x} as \vec{x}' . Then:

$$\vec{x}' = \vec{x} - yr \frac{\vec{w}}{|\vec{w}|}$$

Where multiplying by y just changes the sign for the two cases of \vec{x} being on either side of the decision surface. Moreover, \vec{x}' lies on the decision boundary and so satisfies $\vec{w}^T \vec{x}' + b = 0$.

Hence:

$$\vec{w}^T(\vec{x} - yr\frac{\vec{w}}{|\vec{w}|}) + b = 0$$

Solving for r gives:

$$r = y\frac{\vec{w}^T\vec{x} + b}{|\vec{w}|}$$

Since we can scale the functional margin as we please, for convenience in solving large SVMs, let us choose to require that the functional margin of all data points is at least 1 and that it is equal to 1 for at least one data vector. That is, for all items in the data:

$$y_i(\vec{w}^T\vec{x}_i + b) \geq 1$$

and there exist support vectors for which the inequality is an equality. Since each example's distance from the hyperplane is $r_i = y_i(\vec{w}^T\vec{x}_i + b)/|\vec{w}|$, the geometric margin is $\rho = 2/|\vec{w}|$. Our desire is still to maximize this geometric margin. That is, we want to find \vec{w} and b such that:

- $\rho = 2/|\vec{w}|$ is maximized
- For all $(\vec{x}_i, y_i) \in \mathbb{D}$, $y_i(\vec{w}^T\vec{x}_i + b) \geq 1$

Maximizing $2/|\vec{w}|$ is the same as minimizing $|\vec{w}|/2$. This gives the final standard formulation of an SVM as a minimization problem:

- (K) Find \vec{w} and b such that:
- $\frac{1}{2}\vec{w}^T\vec{w}$ is minimized, and
 - for all $\{(\vec{x}_i, y_i)\}$, $y_i(\vec{w}^T\vec{x}_i + b) \geq 1$

We are now optimizing a quadratic function subject to linear constraints. Quadratic optimization problems are a standard, well-known class of mathematical optimization problems, and many algorithms exist for solving them. We could in principle build our SVM using standard quadratic programming (QP) libraries, but there has been much recent research in this area aiming to exploit the structure of the kind of QP that emerges from an SVM. As a result, there are more intricate but much faster and more scalable libraries available especially for building SVMs, which almost everyone uses to build models. We will not present the details of such algorithms here.

However, it will be helpful to what follows to understand the shape of the solution of such an optimization problem. The solution involves constructing a dual problem where a Lagrange multiplier α_i is associated with each constraint $y_i(\vec{w}^T\vec{x}_i + b) \geq 1$ in the primal problem:

- (L) Find $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_N$ such that $\sum \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_j \alpha_i \alpha_j y_i y_j \vec{x}_i^T \vec{x}_j$ is maximized, and
- $\sum_i \alpha_i y_i = 0$
 - $\alpha_i \geq 0$ for all $1 \leq i \leq N$

The solution is then of the form:

$$(M) \quad \begin{aligned} \vec{w} &= \sum \alpha_i y_i \vec{x}_i \\ b &= y_k - \vec{w}^T \vec{x}_k \text{ for any } \vec{x}_k \text{ such that } \alpha_k \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

In the solution, most of the α_i are zero. Each non-zero α_i indicates that the corresponding \vec{x}_i is a support vector. The classification function is then:

$$f(\vec{x}) = \text{sign}(\sum_i \alpha_i y_i \vec{x}_i^T \vec{x} + b)$$

3.3 KEY POINTS TO REMEMBER [4]

- Learning depends only on dot products of sample pairs.
- Classification depends only on dot products of unknown with samples.
- Exclusive reliance on dot products enables approach to problems in which samples cannot be separated by a straight line.

3.4 KERNEL METHODS

Kernel methods owe their name to the use of kernel functions, which enable them to operate in a high-dimensional, implicit feature space without ever computing the coordinates of the data in that space, but rather by simply computing the inner products between the images of all pairs of data in the feature space. This operation is often computationally cheaper than the explicit computation of the coordinates. This approach is called the "kernel trick". Kernel functions have been introduced for sequence data, graphs, text, images, as well as vectors.

The kernel trick avoids the explicit mapping that is needed to get linear learning algorithms to learn a nonlinear function or decision boundary.

3.5 SVM NON LINEAR CLASSIFIER

In the real world, our dataset is generally dispersed up to some extent. To solve this problem separation of the data into different classes on the basis of straight linear hyper-plane can't be considered a good choice. For this we create non-linear classifiers by applying the kernel trick to maximum-margin hyper-planes. In non-linear SVM classification, data points plotted in a higher dimensional space. [5]

We can draw customized/ non-linear hyper-planes using Kernel trick. Every Kernel holds a non-linear function. This function helps to build a high dimensional feature space. There are many kernels that have been developed. Some of the standard kernels are:

1. Polynomial (homogeneous) Kernel
2. Polynomial (non-homogeneous) Kernel
3. Radial Basis Function Kernel.

3.6 ADVANTAGES & DISADVANTAGES

3.6.1 ADVANTAGE OF SVM CLASSIFIER:

- SVMs are effective when the number of features is quite large.
- It works effectively even if the number of features are greater than the number of samples.
- Non-linear data can also be classified using customized hyper planes built by using kernel trick.
- It is a robust model to solve prediction problems since it maximizes margin.

3.6.2 DISADVANTAGES OF SVM CLASSIFIER:

- The biggest limitation of support Vector Machine is the choice of the kernel. The wrong choice of the kernel can lead to an increase in error percentage.
- With a greater number of samples, it starts giving poor performances.
- SVMs have good generalization performance but they can be extremely slow in the test phase.
- SVMs have high algorithmic complexity and extensive memory requirements due to the use of quadratic programming. [6]

3.7 SVM APPLICATIONS:

SVMs are a byproduct of neural Network. They are widely applied to pattern classification and regression problems. Here are some of its applications:

Facial expression classification: SVMs can be used to classify facial expressions. It uses statistical models of shape and SVMs.

Speech recognition: SVMs are used to accept keywords and reject non-keywords them and build a model recognition speech.

Handwritten digit recognition: Support vector classifiers can be applied to the recognition of isolated handwritten digits optically scanned.

Text Categorization: In information retrieval and then categorization of data using labels can be done by SVM. [7]

Chapter 4

Matlab Implementation

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Handwritten character recognition is a classic machine learning problem, often referred to as the “Hello World” of ML since many programmers start their journey in ML with this problem. Our problem of recognizing basic Bengali character is an example of supervised classification problem. Over the years, Bengali character recognition has gained a considerable interest among the researchers due to emergence of computationally demanding application like data mining and document classification. Contrary to characters from other languages, Bengali characters presents unique set of challenges when trying to train a model.

General steps followed in a machine learning process:

4.2 APPROACH

Bengali characters are very rich in different writing styles. [8] Some of the characters are cursive, some are connected and some are disconnected. Writing styles, writing persons, and the complicated features of the handwritten characters are very challenging for accurately classifying the characters. A feature extraction technique can play an important factor for getting high accuracies in handwritten character recognition systems. But here we have explored a pixel-based approach which directly uses the pattern of the pixels. Pixels are represented as data in high dimensional input space. Without computing any features, we normalized the image into 20x20 pixel space.

4.3 CHOOSING THE RIGHT APPLICATION FOR THE JOB

There are currently many options available for machine learning including Matlab/Octave, Python, R, Keras, C++, Java etc. We have used Matlab 2016b to solve our problem. Primary reasons for choosing Matlab are:

- Function names and signatures are familiar and memorable, making them as easy to write as they are to read.
- Math- and matrix-oriented language, since we will be working with lot of vectors this suits the problem perfectly.
- Comprehensive reference and user documentation.
- Toolboxes like ‘machine learning and statistics toolbox’ along with ‘computer vision’, ‘image processing toolbox’ provide coverage of our problem at hand.
- Comprehensive online help and support are available at Mathworks site and related blogs.

4.4 DATA COLLECTION

One of the most important components of any ML problem is raw data collection. We collected data by employing students from different batches and through kind permission from Computer Vision & Pattern Recognition Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, to use their dataset in our project. CVPRU, ISI conducts research on Optical Character Recognition, Natural Language Processing, Pattern Recognition, Image Processing and Soft Computing tools [9]. The permission is obtained by filling up a form provided by ISI by our supervisor and contracting through email. This process took us several days.

The data obtained from ISI are individual basic Bengali characters and already segmented. Some samples of their data from different classes are showed in Figure 4.1.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

Figure 4.1: Few sample data from ISI haandwritten Bengali basic Character database

It can be seen that, the data provided by ISI are very noisy and of different dimensions. Also the sample classes are highly uneven in size. The most number of samples are from অ and least number of samples are from খ having 740 and 423 samples respectively.

We also took help from forty two 2nd- and 3rd- year students from the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Dhaka to collect samples. Each student filled an A4-sized paper with five characters from each class. This process was prompt and took few hours. They quite happily agreed to help us. Though clear instructions were given to write with a ball pall pen to prevent smudges and spreading, to use the whole space and not to put any extra marks, some students failed to act accrodingly. As a result we could not use few samples sets. Still we are grateful for their contribution.

Few samples of collected data are presented in Figure 4.2.

(a)

ଅ ଆ ଇ ଈ ଉ ଊ କ୍ଷ ଧ ଧ୍ୱ ଓ ଔ
 ଅ ଆ ଇ ଈ ଉ ଊ କ୍ଷ ଧ ଧ୍ୱ ଓ ଔ
 ଅ ଆ ଇ ଈ ଉ ଊ କ୍ଷ ଧ ଧ୍ୱ ଓ ଔ
 ଅ ଆ ଇ ଈ ଉ ଊ କ୍ଷ ଧ ଧ୍ୱ ଓ ଔ
 ଅ ଆ ଇ ଈ ଉ ଊ କ୍ଷ ଧ ଧ୍ୱ ଓ ଔ

(b)

ଞ ଣ ଠ ଡ ଢ କ୍ଷ ଟ ଠ ଓ ଔ
 ଞ ଣ ଠ ଡ ଢ କ୍ଷ ଟ ଠ ଓ ଔ
 ଞ ଣ ଠ ଡ ଢ କ୍ଷ ଟ ଠ ଓ ଔ
 ଞ ଣ ଠ ଡ ଢ କ୍ଷ ଟ ଠ ଓ ଔ
 ଞ ଣ ଠ ଡ ଢ କ୍ଷ ଟ ଠ ଓ ଔ

(c)

(d)

Figure 4.2: Few samples of collected handwritten data for Basic Bengali characters

After scanning the A4 pages, we performed segmentation onto the scanned data. After basic segmentation (without noise removal) we have obtained about 200 samples for each character class. Figure 4.3 shows Few samples after segmentation from first four character classes.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4.3: Some samples from first four classes of locally collected handwritten basic Bengali characters after segmentation

Though the locally collected data are very less noisy compared to that of collected from ISI, these contain more white spaces. These white spaces have been eliminated during data preprocessing.

4.5 DATA PREPROCESSING

Often it is said that the real process of Machine Learning lies in preparing the data and not in training a model. Data preparation takes about 60 to 80 percent of the whole machine learning process [10].

Real world data are generally [11]:

- **Incomplete:** lacking attribute values, lacking certain attributes of interest, or containing only aggregate data
- **Noisy:** containing errors or outliers
- **Inconsistent:** containing discrepancies in codes or names

Tasks in data preprocessing:

- **Data cleaning:** fill in missing values, smooth noisy data, identify or remove outliers, and resolve inconsistencies.

- **Data integration:** using multiple databases, data cubes, or files.
- **Data transformation:** normalization and aggregation.
- **Data reduction:** reducing the volume but producing the same or similar analytical results.

4.5.1 DATA CLEANING

A problem that plagues practical data mining is poor quality of the data [12]. Digital images are prone to a variety of types of noise. Noise is the result of errors in the image acquisition process. It results in pixel values that do not reflect the true intensities of the real scene. There are several ways that noise can be introduced into an image, depending on how the image is created. For example:

[13]

- If the image is scanned from a photograph made on film, the film grain is a source of noise. Noise can also be the result of damage to the film, or be introduced by the scanner itself.
- If the image is acquired directly in a digital format, the mechanism for gathering the data (such as a CCD detector) can introduce noise.
- Electronic transmission of image data can introduce noise.

Three main ways of removing noise from images are: [14]

- Linear Filtering
- Averaging Filter and a Median Filter
- Adaptive Filtering

Data cleaning has been performed on both the locally and imported dataset. Samples from the ISI database and locally collected segmented dataset were quite noisy. The images of all the samples for each basic Bengali character have been converted to binary values and converted to black and white so that all color information are discarded and astray marks are removed. Figure 4.4 shows some noisy data and corresponding binary-converted data.

Figure 4.4: (a) Samples of noisy data and (b) samples of B/W binary-converted data from first four classes of handwritten basic Bengali characters

This process is done by image thresholding in Matlab. Image thresholding is a simple, yet effective, way of partitioning an image into a foreground and background. This image analysis technique is a type of image segmentation that isolates objects by converting grayscale images into binary images. [15] This process also solves the problem of local samples that were of blue ink. Still there are some extra spaces around the characters which have been eliminated in the following stages.

The complete code for noise removal is presented in the Appendix A.

4.5.2 DATA INTEGRATION

Dataset are collected locally and through ISI. Single source and multiple sources are classifications of data quality problems. Single source problems occur in a single database whereas multiple source problems occur whenever data are integrated from two or more sources. [16] When we combined all the data, classes formed are of unequal lengths ranging from almost 1000 samples to around 700 samples. This causes a class imbalance problem.

Class imbalance is the problem in Machine Learning where the total number of samples in a class of data (positive) is far less than the total number samples in another class of data (negative). This problem is extremely common in practice and can be observed in various disciplines including fraud detection, anomaly detection, medical diagnosis, oil spillage detection, facial recognition, etc. [17]

Most Machine Learning algorithms work best when the number of instances of each classes are roughly equal. When the number of instances of one class far exceeds the other, problems arise. If there is a dataset consisting of 10000 genuine and 10 fraudulent transactions, the classifier will

tend to classify fraudulent transactions as genuine transactions. The reason can be easily explained by the numbers. Suppose the machine learning algorithm has two possibly outputs as follows:

1. Model 1 classifies 7 out of 10 fraudulent transactions as genuine transactions and 10 out of 10000 genuine transactions as fraudulent transactions.
2. Model 2 classifies 2 out of 10 fraudulent transactions as genuine transactions and 100 out of 10000 genuine transactions as fraudulent transactions.

If the classifier's performance is determined by the number of mistakes, then clearly Model 1 is better as it makes only a total of 17 mistakes while Model 2 made 102 mistakes. However, as we want to minimize the number of fraudulent transactions happening, we should pick Model 2 instead which only made 2 mistakes classifying the fraudulent transactions. Of course, this could come at the expense of more genuine transactions being classified as fraudulent transactions, but will be a cost we can bear for now. Anyhow, a general machine learning algorithm will just pick Model 1 than Model 2, which is a problem. In practice, this means we will let a lot of fraudulent transactions go through although we could have stopped them by using Model 2. This translates to unhappy customers and money lost for the company.

Ways to mitigate this problem:

- Cost function based approaches
- Sampling based approaches

Sampling based approaches can be sub-divided into:

- Oversampling, by adding more of the minority class so it has more effect on the machine learning algorithm
- Undersampling, by removing some of the majority class so it has less effect on the machine learning algorithm
- Hybrid, a mix of oversampling and undersampling

We have minimized the problem using undersampling process. By undersampling, we could risk removing some of the majority class instances which are more representative, thus discarding useful information. This can be illustrated as follows:

Figure 4.5: Ideal and actual decision boundary lines when (a) a general machine learning algorithm is applied and (b) negative class is under-sampled hence there are false positive points

Here the green line is the ideal decision boundary we would like to have, and blue is the actual result. Figure 4.5 (a) is the result of just applying a general machine learning algorithm without using undersampling. On the other hand, in Figure 4.5 (b), the negative class is undersampled, hence some information of negative class are removed, and the blue decision boundary is caused to be slanted, causing some instances in negative class to be classified as instances of positive class wrongly.

In our work, we solved this problem by randomly choosing 400 samples from ISI dataset and 200 samples from locally collected dataset, keeping our class size to 600.

We avoided going for oversampling because just duplicating the minority classes could lead the classifier to overfitting to a few examples. This would be even a greater problem for our model. Because overfitting is considered to be the largest problem in Machine Learning. [18]

A learning algorithm is trained on a set of training data, but then it is applied to make predictions on new data points. The goal is to maximize its predictive accuracy on the new data points—not necessarily its accuracy on the training data. Indeed, if we work too hard to find the very best fit to the training data, there is a risk that we will memorize the training data rather than finding a general predictive rule. This phenomenon is called “overfitting.” [19]

The fundamental goal of machine learning is to generalize beyond the examples in the training set. So even if something can be predicted with a very high degree of accuracy from a training set, if an accurate prediction in the real world cannot be made, the learner becomes obsolete.

4.5.3 DATA TRANSFORMATION

Machine learning models are only as good as the data that is used to train them. A key characteristic of good training data is that it is provided in a way that is optimized for learning and generalization. The process of putting together the data in this optimal format is known in the industry as data/feature transformation. [20].

Let's consider a machine learning model whose task is to decide whether a credit card transaction is fraudulent or not. Based on application we might decide which data fields (or features) are important to include in the input data. For example, transaction amount, merchant name, address, and credit card owner's address are important to provide to the learning process. On the other hand, a randomly generated transaction ID carries no information, and is not useful.

Once we have decided on which fields to include, we transform these features to help the learning process. Transformations add background experience to the input data, enabling the machine learning model to benefit from this experience. For example, the following merchant address is represented as a string:

"123 Main Street, Seattle, WA 98101"

By itself, the address has limited expressive power – it is useful only for learning patterns associated with that exact address. Breaking it up into constituent parts, however, can create additional features like "Address" (123 Main Street), "City" (Seattle), "State" (WA) and "Zip" (98101). Now, the learning algorithm can group more disparate transactions together, and discover broader patterns – perhaps some merchant zip codes experience more fraudulent activity than others. [21]

We have applied pixel based detection method, our final aim was to convert all binary pixel values of the images into a row vector.

First, we have started processing the samples by removing rows and columns which doesn't include any information; rows and columns which has all 0 values. So, this process converts this image

into this

This caused the image to be of rectangular in shape. We want to maintain 1:1 (length: width) aspect ratio by including minimum possible rows or columns evenly on both sides of the rectangular image. So, we performed bit-padding on all of the images (samples). This caused the rectangular image to be square in shape having 1:1 aspect ratio.

As the image is square in shape we can down convert to smaller resolution maintaining 1:1 aspect ratio. We converted it into 20x20 pixels.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
6	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
7	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 4.6: A 20x20 pixel image is presented as a binary pixel array

The above array is a 20x20 pixel image. From the image we can see that, the black portion of the image is represented as 0 in the array. The shape of the character is represented as 1 in the array. This is conveniently displayed in Microsoft Excel.

Figure 4.7: A 20x20 pixel image presented as a pixel array in Microsoft Excel window

The pixel array has been then converted into a 1x400 elements long or 400 features row vector [6] also known as feature vector. A feature vector is an n-dimensional vector of numerical features that represent some object. Many algorithms in machine learning require a numerical representation of objects, since such representations facilitate processing and statistical analysis. When representing images, the feature values might correspond to the pixels of an image, when representing texts perhaps term occurrence frequencies. [22]

This process is continued for each of 11 classes, each class having 600 samples. Therefore, we get $600 \times 11 = 6600$ feature vector, each one having 400 features.

The complete code for data processing is presented in the Appendix B.

4.5.4 DATA REDUCTION/ DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION

In the supervised learning, a machine-learning algorithm is shown a training set, which is a collection of training examples called instances. After learning from the training set, the learning algorithm is presented with additional input vectors, and the algorithm should generalize, that is to decide what the output value should be.

It is well known that in order to avoid excessive storage and time complexity and to improve generalization accuracy by avoiding noise and overfitting, it is often advisable to reduce original training set by selecting the most representative information [23]. Reducing the size of the dataset can result in:

- increasing capabilities and generalization properties of the classification model,
- reducing space complexity of the classification problem,
- decreasing the required computational time,
- diminishing the size of formulas obtained by an induction algorithm on the reduced data sets

In the real-world situations, relevant features are often unknown a priori and, therefore, many features are introduced with a view to better represent the domain. Many of these features are not only irrelevant from the point of view of classification results but also can have a negative influence on the accuracy and on the required learning time of the classifier. The presence of redundant features introduces unnecessary noise to the data mining analysis and results in the increased computational complexity of the learning process. As it has been observed, the number

of instances needed to assure the required classification accuracy grows exponentially with the number of irrelevant features present.

Basic Data reduction often includes: [11]

- Reducing the number of attributes
- Reducing the number of attribute values
- Reducing the number of tuples

Few state-of-the-art techniques on dimensionality reduction currently available and accepted in the data analytics landscape:

- Missing Values Ratio.
- Low Variance Filter.
- High Correlation Filter.
- Random Forests / Ensemble Trees.
- Principal Component Analysis (PCA).
- Backward Feature Elimination.
- Forward Feature Construction.

We have performed data reduction by Matlab's built in PCA function which has shown significant rise in accuracy.

More about the Matlab PCA function is included in the Appendix C.

4.6 DEFINING CLASS

Since this is a supervised learning, we need to provide the output or class name of each class vector. So, we have assigned each of the 11 character classes a unique class number from 0 to 10 (Table 4.1).

Table 4.1

Class name	Class
0	ଅ
1	ଓ
2	ଧ
3	ନ
4	ମ
5	ତ
6	କ
7	ଞ
8	ଝ
9	ଞ
10	ଝ

As for the class naming, we added another column of our feature vector array mentioning the class name of the vector. Therefore first 600 vectors have an extra 401st column 1, second 600 column 2 and so on until the last 600 vectors have an extra column of 10. This column will be set as output or ‘Response’ during the training of the model.

4.7 TRAINING THE MODEL

After data processing, for training our model, we have used Matlab's built-in 'Classification Learner' app. Classification Learner app trains models to classify data. Using this app, we can explore supervised machine learning using various classifiers. We can explore your data, select features, specify validation schemes, train models, and assess results. We can perform automated training to search for the best classification model type, including decision trees, discriminant analysis, support vector machines, logistic regression, nearest neighbors, and ensemble classification.

From the 'APPS' we selected 'Classification Learner' and then started a new session. From the workspace we imported the variable which holds 401x600 vectors into the learner. We selected first 400 column as 'Predictor' or input features and 401st column as 'Response' or output class name. Cross-validation folds have been selected as 20 folds. We started the training session by pressing 'Start Session' (Figure 4.8). More about cross-validation is presented in Appendix D.

Figure 4.8: A new session in 'Classification Learner' app

Figure 4.9: Classification learner- Scatter Plot window showing different classifiers while calculating accuracy of the classification process

From the drop-down list containing the list of different algorithms we choose ‘All’ and press ‘Train’. Training took some time. Then, after training all the classifiers, we noticed cubic SVM classifier has the highest rate of accuracy. We further performed several ‘Advanced’ techniques on the cubic SVM classifier to obtain a better accuracy.

4.7.1 ADVANCED TECHNIQUES PERFORMED ON CUBIC SVM

We have used all the features out of 400 and relied on PCA for data reduction. We have set kernel scale to 10, box constraint level 1, and choose multi class method as one-vs-all as opposed to default value one-vs-one. It took us a total of 21 one iterations to get the maximum accuracy of 86.7%.

20 ☆ SVM	Accuracy: 85.8%
Last change: 'KernelScale' = '11'	60/400 features (PCA on)
21 ☆ SVM	Accuracy: 86.7%
Last change: PCA keeping 70 numeric components	70/400 features (PCA on)
22 ☆ SVM	Accuracy: 86.3%
Last change: PCA keeping 75 numeric components	75/400 features (PCA on)

Figure 4.10: Advanced techniques performed on cubic SVM

We later exported the selected classifier into the workspace for our own testing.

4.7.2 PARTICULARS ABOUT THE CHOSEN CLASSIFIER

Particulars about the chosen classifier are given below:

Model Number: 21

Status: Trained

Accuracy: 86.7%

Prediction Speed: ~1100 obs/sec

Training Time: 27.803 sec

Classifier

Preset: Cubic SVM

Kernel Function: Cubic

Kernel scale: 10

Box constraint level: 1

Multiclass method: One-vs-All

Standardize data: true

Feature Selection

All features used in the model, before PCA

PCA

After training, 70 components were kept

Explained variance per component (in order): 6.8%, 3.5%, 2.8%, 2.2%, 2.0%, 1.8%, 1.7%, 1.6%, 1.5%, 1.4% (variance of least important components hidden)

4.8 SUMMARY

In this chapter, we mainly focused on the Matlab implementation of the machine learning algorithm we performed for the recognition of handwritten Bengali basic characters. We started with data collection from two sources: local and external. After proper segmentation of data, we processed and under-sampled all the data, removed noise by changing the images into binary valued Black-and-white 20x20 images through the thresholding method in Matlab. Bit-padding

has been done to give an even square shape (1:1 aspect ratio) to all the image samples. Then, we arranged these images in pixel arrays and finally converted into feature vectors. We assigned a unique number from 0 to 10 to each of the 11 basic character classes and the trained the model using Matlab's built-in 'classification learner' app where the selected classifier was cubic SVM with highest 86.7% accuracy. In the following chapter, we are going to discuss the results.

Chapter 5

Performance Results Analysis

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Since we have trained our model we will analyze the accuracy of our model both by using standard performance measure tools and manual data input.

Matlab provides quite a few number of standard tools which we will use to test the performance of our model. The tools include confusion matrix and ROC curve.

We will be analyzing the standard tools for first four classes. They are:

Class name	Class
0	০
1	১
2	২
3	৩

5.2 CONFUSION MATRIX

A confusion matrix summarizes the classification performance of a classifier with respect to some test data. It is a two-dimensional matrix, indexed in one dimension by the true class of an object and in the other by the class that the classifier assigns. Table 5.1 presents an example of confusion matrix for a three-class classification task, with the classes A, B, and C. [24]

Table 5.1: Confusion Matrix (An example of three class confusion matrix)

		Assigned Class		
		A	B	C
Actual Class	A	10	2	1
	B	0	6	1
	C	0	3	8

The first row of the matrix indicates that 13 objects belong to the class A and that 10 are correctly classified as belonging to A, two misclassified as belonging to B, and one as belonging to C.

In this context, the four cells of the matrix are designated as true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN) as indicated in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Confusion Matrix (The outcomes of classification into positive and negative classes)

		Assigned Class	
		Positive	Negative
Actual Class	Positive	TP	FN
	Negative	FP	TN

A number of measures of classification performance are defined in terms of these four classification outcomes.

- Specificity = True negative rate = $TN / (TN+FP)$
- Sensitivity = True positive rate = **Recall** = $TP / (TP+FN)$
- Positive predictive value = **Precision** = $TP / (TP+FP)$
- Negative predictive value = $TN / (TN+ FN)$

We plotted our confusion matrix for our model for first four classes (Model 21):

Figure 5.1: Confusion matrix plotted for first four character classes of model 21 in MATLAB

As we see from our model’s confusion matrix, the green diagonal cells, which represented numbers of correct prediction of class is 85% or higher. We also see from here that highest false negative for each class is also the adjacent class. Which means the highest confusion which occurs during prediction is between similar looking characters like **অ** and **আ** or **ই** and **ঐ**. The overall accuracy of our model 86.7%. So, we can confidently say true positive rate for other class is around 85%.

5.3 ROC CURVE

The Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve is a plot depicting the trade-off between the true positive rate and the false positive rate for a classifier under varying decision thresholds. ROC graphs are a useful and clear possibility for organizing classifiers and visualizing their quality (performance). The research started in about 1940's to explain and interpret radio signals, used by radar receivers to analyze radar images during World War II. From the beginning of 1970's it was found as useful tool for interpreting medical test results and other problems. ROC graphs are now commonly used in medical and other decision making, and in recently has been adopted in the machine learning and data mining research communities. [25]

Accuracy is measured by the area under the ROC curve (AUC). An area of 1 represents a perfect test; an area of .5 represents a worthless test. A rough guide for classifying the accuracy of a diagnostic test is the traditional academic point system: [26]

.90-1 = excellent (A)

.80-.90 = good (B)

.70-.80 = fair (C)

.60-.70 = poor (D)

.50-.60 = fail (F)

Figure 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5 show areas under ROC curve for positive classes 0, 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 5.2: Area Under ROC Curve for positive class 0

For positive class 0, AUC=0.97

Figure 5.3: Area under ROC curve for positive class 1

For positive class 1, AUC=0.98

Figure 5.4: Area under ROC curve for positive class 2

For positive class 2, AUC=0.98

Figure 5.5: Area under ROC curve for positive class 3

For positive class 3, AUC=0.97

Areas of the ROC curve for the first four classes of our model come well above .90 giving an excellent accuracy.

5.4 MANUAL DATA INPUT

We keep aside a test set of 10 samples from each class for later testing. We manually input the data doing the same pre-processing into the imported classifier in the workspace. The results we get is tabulated Table 5.3.

Table 5.3

Class	Number of correct predictions	Percentage accuracy
0	8	80%
1	7	70%
2	9	90%
3	9	90%
4	6	60%
5	7	70%
6	8	80%
7	7	70%
8	9	90%
9	9	90%
10	8	80%

Overall percentage accuracy in manual testing = 79.0%

5.5 SUMMARY

In this chapter, we have analyzed the accuracy of our trained model by using confusion matrix and area under the ROC curve. For this analysis, we have considered first four character classes. After plotting a 4x4 confusion matrix for these four classes, we got minimum 85% correct prediction for each class. We also calculated areas under ROC curve for each character class and the result was

excellent. Then we went through manual data input process. Overall percentage accuracy in manual testing was 79.0%.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The sheer volume of available information has grown exponentially over the past five years, and new tools have been developed for turning this flood of raw data into insights. It is a miracle that we can make sense of the information, that to human is meaningless.

Machine Learning algorithm is a computer program that teaches computers how to program themselves so that we don't have to explicitly describe how to perform the task we want to achieve. The information that a Machine Learning algorithm needs in order to write its own program to solve a particular task is a set of known examples. The task of teaching a computer to identify animals, we will show to the computer a bunch of labeled pictures (e.g. this picture is a tiger, this picture is a cat, etc.), the same way we do it when we teach children.

Our model which we have designed to know about Bengali vowels knows and accurately detects better than a toddler.

6.2 SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

In Chapter 2 we talk about some of the more popular machine learning algorithms that we have mentioned earlier, linear regression, logistic regression, k-means, naïve Bayes, k nearest neighbours, neural network and support vector machine, tree, ensemble etc. For classification purpose we trained tree, discriminant, SVM, KNN and ensemble algorithms. We finally picked SVM as our desired algorithm based on its learning accuracy. In Chapter 3 we talk about SVM in detail. Its mathematical basis, kernel function, and its usage in the industry.

SVM is a popular choice for handwritten character recognition for its high accuracy. It has been observed, almost always a SVM classifier outperform all other classifiers in handwritten character recognition problem. [27]. We got a similar result in our project supporting our choice for SVM.

6.3 MATLAB IMPLEMENTATION

In Chapter 4, we tried to implement our knowledge of machine learning algorithms and Matlab to find a practical solution. As for any machine learning problem data collection and processing is the major obstacle to overcome. Our data came from two sources. We collected one third of our final dataset locally. The other two third of our dataset was provided by Indian Statistical Institute upon knowing our intention.

The main problem we faced during data preprocessing was segmentation. Unlike English characters, almost all Bengali characters requires two or more strokes to complete. Gaps sometimes occurs between the strokes which makes automatic segmentation trickier, as Matlab detects the separate strokes as two distinct images. We partly solved the problem by using a Gaussian filter to smear out the image so that the gap joins. In case of bigger gaps we had to manually crop out the image.

The other processes like noise removal, image binarization, resize, and converting them into feature vectors was done without any problem.

We have trained the model once at first using all the learning algorithms we obtain a preliminary idea as to what algorithm will suit best for our project and give the highest accuracy. All types of SVM (linear SVM, quadratic SVM, cubic SVM, fine Gaussian SVM, medium Gaussian, coarse Gaussian SVM) came out in the top, and among them cubic SVM had the highest accuracy. So we went ahead with cubic SVM and trained it multiple times, each time changing its PCA, kernel scale, box-constraint level and cross validation folds. Changing the technique to one vs all from one vs one, increased the accuracy of our classifier significantly.

After many iterations we choose the 21st model since it has the highest accuracy.

6.4 PERFORMANCE RESULTS ANALYSIS

We have used three techniques to analyze the performance of our trained model. Firstly we have used confusion matrix to see the prediction rate for the first four class. The lowest true positive rate was 85% which is good enough since our overall accuracy was 86.7%.

Then we did a ROC analysis. Accuracy is measured by the area under the ROC curve (AUC). An area of 1 represents a perfect test; an area of .5 represents a worthless test. A rough guide for classifying the accuracy of a diagnostic test is the traditional academic point system:

- .90-1 = excellent (A)
- .80-.90 = good (B)
- .70-.80 = fair (C)
- .60-.70 = poor (D)
- .50-.60 = fail (F)

All of the AUC of the first four classes came out to be .97, .98, .98, .97 respectively.

Then we did a manual test on the model using a test set of 10 characters per class. The accuracy came out to be less than the overall accuracy. We have determined this is due to the very small test set we have used. We couldn't set aside a very large test set as some class were very small in size. A higher accuracy is expected if the test is done on a much bigger test set.

All in all we are pleased with our results, given the time constraints and limitations.

6.5 LIMITATIONS

Our classifier to be put to any practical use needs to be changed. Limitations of our present classifier can be solved by:

- Firstly a practical classifier needs to account for all the characters (vowels, consonants, consonant conjuncts, modifiers and numeric characters) in Bengali language. Right now it can only predict vowels.
- We have trained our model on a comparatively small dataset. Confusion matrix shows it still has a high false negative rate for adjacent classes. Most handwritten recognition classifiers are trained by tens of thousands of samples. MNIST database has 60000 train and 10000 test samples for English characters. We have no such samples for Bengali characters. We have to take a huge initiative preferably by universities to make a huge nationwide dataset.

6.6 IMPROVEMENT OF CURRENT MODEL

Accuracy of a model can be increased by:

- Collect data: Increase the number of training examples
- Feature processing: Add more variables and better feature processing
- Model parameter tuning: Consider alternate values for the training parameters used by your learning algorithm

So far we have used the third technique to increase the accuracy of our model as much as possible. We have experimented changing cross-validated values, PCA, and kernel scale to maximize the accuracy of our model.

But it can only increase so far, without trying the other two factors. We have to use small amount of data (600 per class) to train our model. Due to class imbalance we had to undersample our dataset. A higher data sample per class, preferably 2000 sample per class would be ideal in our situation.

Another way the model's accuracy could be increased is by introducing distorted, noisy images and rotated images. Which is expected in real life scenarios. This will be done in future experiments.

We have kept our feature size to 400 to reduce training time, size and complexity. A model with more feature is believed to be more accurate.

6.7 PRACTICAL USE

One practical way how we have already used the model, is connecting a webcam with the Matlab and continuously predict any Bengali letter in front of it. The accuracy is a little than that found for manually inputting values. It is found that the webcam image is hazy and introduces a lot of noise.

The webcam used is Logitech C270.

6.8 FUTURE SCOPE

We have plans to include a voice feedback to the system which will speak out the character upon detection. This could help visually impaired people to read. Another use could be a learning tool for children.

In future we would like to expand our project to include consonants, consonant conjuncts, modifiers and numeric characters, and train the model in excess of 2000 samples per class.

Finally I would like to conclude my project with a quote:

“A breakthrough in machine learning would be worth ten Microsofts.”

-Bill Gates

Appendix A

```
%% noise removal
imagen=double(imbinarize(a,'adaptive','ForegroundPolarity','dark','Sensitivit
y',0.4));
threshold = graythresh(a);
imagen =~im2bw(a,threshold);
```

Appendix B

```
%% removing excess white border
imagen( ~any(imagen,2), : ) = []; %rows
imagen( :, ~any(imagen,1) ) = []; %columns

%% paddding
[rows columns]=size(imagen);
if columns>rows
    offset=columns-rows;
    if mod(offset,2)~=0
        pad=offset/2;
        pad1=pad+.5;
        pad2=pad-.5;
        D = padarray(imagen,[pad1 0],'pre');
        D = padarray(D,[pad2 0],'post');
    elseif mod(offset,2)==0
        pad1=offset/2;
        pad2=offset/2;
        D = padarray(imagen,[pad1 0],'pre');
        D = padarray(D,[pad2 0],'post');
    end
elseif rows>columns
    offset=rows-columns;
    if mod(offset,2)~=0
        pad=offset/2;
        pad1=pad+.5;
        pad2=pad-.5;
        D = padarray(imagen,[0 pad1],'pre');
        D = padarray(D,[0 pad2],'post');
    elseif mod(offset,2)==0
        pad1=offset/2;
        pad2=offset/2;
        D = padarray(imagen,[0 pad1],'pre');
        D = padarray(D,[0 pad2],'post');
    end
else
    D=imagen;
```

end

Appendix C

One of the difficulties inherent in multivariate statistics is the problem of visualizing data that has many variables. But when there are more than three variables, it is more difficult to visualize their relationships.

Fortunately, in data sets with many variables, groups of variables often move together. One reason for this is that more than one variable might be measuring the same driving principle governing the behavior of the system. In many systems there are only a few such driving forces. But an abundance of instrumentation enables you to measure dozens of system variables. When this happens, you can take advantage of this redundancy of information. You can simplify the problem by replacing a group of variables with a single new variable.

Principal component analysis is a quantitatively rigorous method for achieving this simplification. The method generates a new set of variables, called principal components. Each principal component is a linear combination of the original variables. All the principal components are orthogonal to each other, so there is no redundant information. The principal components as a whole form an orthogonal basis for the space of the data.

There are an infinite number of ways to construct an orthogonal basis for several columns of data. What is so special about the principal component basis?

The first principal component is a single axis in space. When you project each observation on that axis, the resulting values form a new variable. And the variance of this variable is the maximum among all possible choices of the first axis.

The second principal component is another axis in space, perpendicular to the first. Projecting the observations on this axis generates another new variable. The variance of this variable is the maximum among all possible choices of this second axis.

The full set of principal components is as large as the original set of variables. But it is commonplace for the sum of the variances of the first few principal components to exceed 80% of the total variance of the original data. By examining plots of these few new variables, researchers often develop a deeper understanding of the driving forces that generated the original data.

Appendix D

Cross-validation is a model assessment technique used to evaluate a machine learning algorithm's performance in making predictions on new datasets that it has not been trained on. This is done by partitioning a dataset and using a subset to train the algorithm and the remaining data for testing.

Because cross-validation does not use all of the data to build a model, it is a commonly used method to prevent overfitting during training.

Each round of cross-validation involves randomly partitioning the original dataset into a training set and a testing set. The training set is then used to train a supervised learning algorithm and the testing set is used to evaluate its performance. This process is repeated several times and the average cross-validation error is used as a performance indicator.

Common cross-validation techniques include:

k-fold: Partitions data into k randomly chosen subsets (or folds) of roughly equal size. One subset is used to validate the model trained using the remaining subsets. This process is repeated k times such that each subset is used exactly once for validation.

Holdout: Partitions data into exactly two subsets (or folds) of specified ratio for training and validation.

Leaveout: Partitions data using the k -fold approach where k is equal to the total number of observations in the data. Also known as leave-one-out cross-validation.

Repeated random sub-sampling: Performs Monte Carlo repetitions of randomly partitioning data and aggregating results over all the runs.

Stratify: Partitions data such that both training and test sets have roughly the same class proportions in the response or target.

Resubstitution: Does not partition the data; uses the training data for validation. Often produces overly optimistic estimates for performance and must be avoided if there is sufficient data.

Cross-validation can be a computationally intensive operation since training and validation is done several times. Because each partition set is independent, this analysis can be performed in parallel to speed up the process.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1]. Ed Newton. “Medium”. Medium Corporation, December 29, 2016. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://medium.com/on-coding/what-is-machine-learning-and-why-is-it-important-4255000e19bc>
- [2]. Bernard Marr. “Forbes”. Forbes, FEB 19, 2016. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2016/02/19/a-short-history-of-machine-learning-every-manager-should-read/#1a68681315e7>
- [3]. Christopher D. Manning, Prabhakar Raghavan & Hinrich Schütze. “Introduction to Information Retrieval”. Cambridge University Press. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://nlp.stanford.edu/IR-book/html/htmledition/support-vector-machines-the-linearly-separable-case-1.html>
- [4]. Prof. Patrick Henry Winston. “Artificial Intelligence”. MIT OpenCourseWare. (Web). March 31, 2107. <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/electrical-engineering-and-computer-science/6-034-artificial-intelligence-fall-2010/>
- [5]. Steinwart, Ingo, Christmann, Andreas. *Support Vector Machines*. Springer, 2008. Print.
- [6]. Andrew Ng. “Machine Learning by Stanford”. Coursera. (Web). Jan 10, 2016. <https://www.coursera.org/learn/machine-learning/lecture/sKQoJ/using-an-svm>
- [7]. “Support vector machine”. Wikipedia (Web). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Support_vector_machine
- [8]. Olarik Surinta, Lambert Schomaker and Marco Wiering, *A Comparison of Feature and Pixel-based Methods for Recognizing Handwritten Bangla Digits*, Institute of Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Engineering, University of Groningen.
- [9]. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Unit, Indian Statistical Institute. (Web) <http://www.isical.ac.in/~cvpr/>
- [10]. Kai Wähler. “Infoq”. InfoQ: Software Development News, Videos & Books, Mar 05, 2017. <https://www.infoq.com/articles/ml-data-processing>
- [11]. Prof. Zdravko Markov, department of Computer Science, Central Connecticut State University. <http://www.cs.ccsu.edu/~markov/>
- [12]. Ian H. Witten, Eibe Frank, Mark A. Hall. *Data Mining - Practical Machine Learning Tools and Techniques, third edition*. ELSEVIER. 2011. Print
- [13]. “Noise Removal”. Mathworks. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://www.mathworks.com/help/images/noise-removal.html>

- [14]. “Image Thresholding”. Mathworks. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://www.mathworks.com/discovery/image-thresholding.html>
- [15]. “Analyzing images using image thresholding techniques”. Mathworks. (Web). March 31, 2017. <https://www.mathworks.com/discovery/image-thresholding.html>
- [16]. Natarajan K., Li J., Koronios A. (2010) *Data mining techniques for data cleaning*. In: Kiritsis D., Emmanouilidis C., Koronios A., Mathew J. (eds) *Engineering Asset Lifecycle Management*. Springer, London
- [17]. “Class Imbalance Problem”. (Web). March 31, 2017. <http://www.chioka.in/class-imbalance-problem/>
- [18]. Pedro Domingos, Department of Computer Science and Engineering University of Washington, *A Few Useful Things to Know about Machine Learning*, Communications of the ACM Volume 55 Issue 10, October 2012
- [19]. Tom Dietterich, Oregon State Univ., Corvallis, *Overfitting and undercomputing in machine learning*, ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR), Volume 27 Issue 3, Sept. 1995, Pages 326-327
- [20]. “Data Transformations for Machine Learning”. Amazon Web Service. (Web). March 31, 2017. <http://docs.aws.amazon.com/machine-learning/latest/dg/data-transformations-for-machine-learning.html>
- [21]. “Importance of Feature Transformation”. Amazon Web Service. (Web). March 31, 2017. <http://docs.aws.amazon.com/machine-learning/latest/dg/importance-of-feature-transformation.html>
- [22]. “Feature vector”. Wikipedia. (Web). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Feature_vector
- [23]. Czarnowski I., Jędrzejowicz P. (2008) *Data Reduction Algorithm for Machine Learning and Data Mining*. In: Nguyen N.T., Borzemski L., Grzech A., Ali M. (eds) *New Frontiers in Applied Artificial Intelligence*. IEA/AIE 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 5027. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg
- [24]. Claude Sammut, Geoffrey I. Webb. *Encyclopedia of Machine Learning*. Edition 1. Springer US. 2010 (Print).
- [25]. Antonin Slaby, University of Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic. *ROC Analysis with Matlab*. Hrvatski nacionalni korpus
- [26]. Thomas G. Tape, MD, University of Nebraska, “The Area Under an ROC Curve”, (Web). March 31, 2017. <http://gim.unmc.edu/dxtests/roc3.htm>
- [27]. Tapan Kumar BhowmikPradip GhantyAnandarup RoySwapan Kumar Parui. *SVM-based hierarchical architectures for handwritten Bangla character recognition*. International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJ DAR), July 2009, Volume 12, Issue 2, pp 97–108